

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

**Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the
Southern Ocean**

Deliverable D3.3

OCEAN:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

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About this document

Deliverable: D3.3 Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the Southern Ocean

Work Package: WP3 Ice sheet mass balance, forcing and dynamics

Delivery date: 30 April 2024

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	30 April 2024	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	10 October 2024	Revision after the 1 st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The section 1 has been slightly revised with info on the velocities. 2) The captions of Fig. 6 and Fig.7 have been integrated. 3) The text below the Fig. 7 caption has been also enhanced with requested details. 4) The section 4 has been revised and enhanced. Delivery to the European Commission.	A: G. Hilmar Gudmundsson, Max Brils (UNN) R: C. Bearzotti (DMI)

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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable relates to the modelling and quantification of basal melt rates produced within the interior of the Antarctic Ice Sheet due to basal sliding. As ice slides over the glacier bed, frictional heat is produced causing melting of basal ice. Calculating the resulting rate of meltwater productions involves estimating two quantities: the speed by which the ice slides over the bed, and the stresses acting on the bed through the flow of ice. We used state-of-the-art data assimilation methods to estimate those quantities, whereby measurements of surface velocities, as reported by ITS_LIVE, serve to tightly constrain physical model parameters related to ice flow. This gave us a new estimate of basal water production for the whole of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. In areas of high flow, we find that basal water production is on the order of a few meters per year. In comparison, basal water production due to geothermal heat flux is typically on the order of a few millimetres, or in other words: three orders of magnitude smaller. Furthermore, due to the absence of reliable estimates of the geothermal heat flux, estimates of related basal-water production are at best educated guesses. In contrast, our estimates of basal water production due to sliding are highly constrained by measurements. Additionally, we have developed a new water-routing algorithm and applied this to the key areas of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. The new subglacial water-routing algorithm does not suffer from mesh-resolution dependency issues, as some previously published approaches to this problem (Le Brocq et al. 2009) and does not require a separate “filling algorithm” to fill local depressions in the water potential.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

The work performed involved modelling basal meltwater production from the Antarctic Ice Sheet to the Southern Ocean. As ice slides over the bed, heat is generated and becomes available for basal melt. The initial task was to provide an estimate of the resulting water production. This is a non-trivial problem because it involves estimating both basal sliding velocities and basal drag and can only be done by first performing a model inversion to estimate basal properties. Once this has been done, a further objective is to establish a methodology for routing the resulting water production towards the grounding lines.

We have already produced new maps of basal melt water production, which we arrived at by performing a pan-Antarctic inversion of surface velocities. We found that the key areas of water production are those upstream of Pine Island and Thwaites glaciers.

Furthermore, we have made significant progress in developing a new and novel framework for routing the resulting water towards the grounding lines. A special emphasis has been placed on make sure that the resulting modelling framework is mass-conserving and the results mesh-independent. This issue of mesh-independence has been mentioned repeatedly in previous publications, but we know believe we have overcome this issue.

Using this new approach, we have calculated subglacial water fluxes from the interior of the Antarctic Ice Sheet into the Southern Ocean. Thus, all intended objectives of the deliverable have now been achieved.

The new water-routing model has been incorporated into an open-access community ice-sheet model (<https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource/wiki>). The results will be further communicated at an upcoming symposium of the International Glaciological Society on *Verification and Validation of*

*Cryospheric Models*¹, and a publication is in preparation for the open access journal *Annals of Glaciology*.

2.2 Development of a subglacial water-routing algorithm

A new water-routing algorithm has been developed and tested. It is based on solving,

$$\partial_t h_w + \nabla \cdot (q_w) = a_w$$

where h_w is a water-film thickness, q_w , the water flux vector, and a_w the subglacial water production. The water flux vector is related to the hydraulic potential ϕ as follows,

$$q_w = -k h_w \nabla \phi$$

where k is related to the (effective) permeability, and

$$\phi = g(\rho_w - \rho_i)B + g(\rho_w - \rho_i)h_w + g\rho_i s - N$$

where B , s , ρ_i , ρ_w , is the bedrock, upper surface, ice, and water densities, respectively, and N is the effective water pressure. The system is subject to the positive water-film thickness constraint,

$$h_w > 0$$

The system was solved using finite elements, and a fully implicit non-linear solver with respect to h_w based on Newton-Raphson iteration. The water-film thickness constraint was fulfilled using the active-set algorithm.

The hydraulic potential ϕ can be written as

$$\phi = \Theta + Y - N$$

where

$$Y = g(\rho_w - \rho_i)h_w$$

and

$$\Theta = g(\rho_w - \rho_i)B$$

And N is the effective pressure. We therefore have two unknowns, the effective water pressure (N), and the water film thickness (h_w). To close the system, we therefore need an additional evolutionary equation for N . For routing purposes, it is however presumably sufficient to evolve h_w only and set $N = 0$. This is a common approach in subglacial water-routing modelling (DE FLEURIAN et al. 2018), and sometimes it is furthermore assumed that h_w does not evolve either (Le Brocq et al. 2009). However, here we do evolve h_w with time. The advantage of evolving h_w is that no separate “filling” algorithm is required. Thus, the system we solve is fully described by the system,

$$\partial_t h_w - \nabla \cdot (\kappa h_w \nabla h_w) - \nabla \cdot (k h_w \nabla \Theta) = a_w$$

This is a non-linear diffusion equation. We solve this in its weak form, i.e.

$$(\partial_t h_w, \psi) + (\kappa h_w \nabla h_w, \nabla \psi) + (k h_w \nabla \Theta, \nabla \psi) = (a_w, \psi)$$

¹ https://www.igsoc.org/event/northumbria_2024

where the bracket (\cdot, \cdot) denotes an L^2 inner product. Here $\kappa = k g (\rho_w - \rho_i)$, where k is the (effective) hydraulic permeability, which is a poorly constrained parameter.

Comparing this approach with that of (Le Brocq et al. 2009), we here assume that

$$N = 0, \Upsilon \neq 0$$

while Le Brock et al (2009) assume

$$N = 0, \Upsilon = 0$$

In Le Brock et al (2009) the hydrological potential does not evolve, and the water flow direction is fixed and unchangeable. As a result, the Le Brock et al (2009) algorithm requires an additional “filling” algorithm to ensure that water does not accumulate indefinitely in local minima of the prescribed and unchangeable hydrological potential. Here, on the other hand, the hydrological potential changes over time, and with it the flow direction, and therefore no separate filling algorithm is required.

2.3 Open Science

Our results will be published in an open-access journal. The target journal is an upcoming issue of *Annals of Glaciology* (IGS) related to the topic of model verification and validation.

The results will be presented at an international conference organized by the International Glaciological Society on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models.

Additionally, our newly developed subglacial water-routing algorithm has been added as an additional module to the open-source ice-sheet model *Úa*.

All the program code is publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource>, and the description of the algorithm is now included in the publicly available documentation of the ice-flow model, *UaCompendium*: <https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource/blob/master/UaCompendium.pdf>

The end-users are likely to be scientist interested in ice and ocean dynamics and graduate and postgraduate students. The software is fully tested and available to end-users on Github. We organize annual international user meetings (next one planned for August 2024) and the new options provided by the software will be explained and communicated to new and all existing users. Students will be able to use the software for new dissertation projects.

3. Results

Basal meltwater production of Antarctic

New pan-Antarctic surface-to-bed inversions were performed using the ice-sheet model *Úa*². We found that Pine Island and Thwaites glaciers produce up to 1 to 1.2 m/yr of meltwater over significant areas upstream of their respective grounding lines. This is several orders of magnitude larger than the often-quoted value of about 1 mm/yr (e.g. see the widely used textbook for glaciology *Physics of Glaciers*, Paterson).

² <https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource/wiki>

Fig. 1: Meltwater production for section of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet. Note the logarithmic scale. This area showed the largest meltwater production of all the sectors of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. Note that this is meltwater production due to basal sliding alone. While we have not routed this water production specifically yet, it is clear that the water will be routed directly downstream to the respective grounding lines.

We have produced maps of basal ice-sheet water productions for Antarctica. Our next step will be to work with our partners within the project and estimate the most appropriate spatial resolution. Currently our products use a spatially variable resolution, as is typical of ice-flow models that use unstructured computational grids.

Fig. 2: Meltwater production for the whole of Antarctic Ice Sheet. Note the logarithmic scale. This result was based on performing a surface-to-bed velocity inversion for the basal slipperiness, and then calculating the generated heat flux generated through basal sliding.

Our inversion products were obtained using Weertman sliding law, which is the most-commonly used sliding law in ice-sheet modelling. Additionally, we performed inversions using several other sliding laws that are used in ice-flow modelling studies, such as the Tsai sliding law, and sliding laws based on combinations of Weertman and Coulomb sliding.

We conducted extensive tests to ensure that the water-routing algorithm is mass conserving and to establish mesh convergence. Towards this end we designed new numerical tests based on a synthetic geometry shown in Fig. 3, and established that calculated flux through flux gates equals total upstream water production, see Fig. 5.

Fig. 3: Synthetic test geometry. The bedrock geometry includes retrograde sections and peaks and troughs in both upper and lower surfaces.

Fig. 4: Modelled water fluxes based on geometry in Fig. 1. The arrows indicate flux vectors. The thick black circle is the flux gate for which the fluxes shown in Fig. 3 were calculated.

Fig. 5: Example of a test where total flux through a flux gate is compared to total integrated basal water production upstream of the flux gate. In steady state these numbers must be equal. The figure shows excellent agreement between calculated flux values (circles) and total integrated updates melt-water production (dashed line). The analytical steady state value is $\pi r^2 a$, where r is the radius of the flux gate shown in Fig 2, and $a = 10 \text{ m/yr}$ is the prescribed meltwater production.

Modelled meltwater fluxes

Fig. 6: Map of the modelled meltwater fluxes for Pine Island and Thwaites Glacier. These two glaciers are of special interest due to their large current contribution to sea-level rise. The figure shows the meltwater fluxes due to frictional heating at the base. Blue lines indicate the ice shelf front, whereas red lines indicate the position of the grounding line. As recommended by SCAR'S geographic information committee, the figure uses the internationally accepted Antarctic Polar Stereographic system (EPSG:3031, with Cartesian 2D CS for south polar azimuthal lon 0°E. Axes: E,N. Orientations: E along 90°E, N along 0°E meridians. UoM: m). And as is done in almost all scientific publications we display the x-axis from left to right, and the y-axis from down to up.

Fig. 7: Map of the modelled meltwater fluxes for Siple Ice Coast, Antarctica. Blue lines indicate the ice shelf front, whereas red lines indicate the position of the grounding line. As recommended by SCAR'S geographic information committee, the figure uses the internationally accepted Antarctic Polar Stereographic system (EPSG:3031, with Cartesian 2D CS for south polar azimuthal lon 0°E. Axes: E,N. Orientations: E along 90°E, N along 0°E meridians. UoM: m). And as is done in almost all scientific publications we display the x-axis from left to right, and the y-axis from down to up.

Modelled subglacial water fluxes for key areas of the Antarctic Ice Sheet are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The simulation was done at 7 km resolution using linear triangular elements. While the general order-of-magnitude of the fluxes is similar to some previously published results (e.g. (see Fig2c in Le Brocq et al. 2009) the spatial distribution of the water fluxes is significantly different. This could be related to differences in the value of the effective hydraulic conductivity, which is a poorly constrained model parameter. Since observations of subglacial meltwater production rates underneath the Antarctic Ice Sheet do not exist, these model results present a novel and important constraint on their contribution to sea-level rise and their oceanic impact. On the other hand, this means that it is impossible to compare the modelled volume fluxes with observations.

References

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4. Impact

This deliverable is contributing to the following project objectives (O) listed in the description of the action.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models.

We have developed new algorithm to estimate water fluxes into the Southern Ocean. This process is potentially critical for the meltwater plume dynamics and likely to impact estimates of ocean-induced melt in coupled ice-ocean models. This will then impact ice-shelf melt and subsequent sea-level rise. The new algorithm has been incorporated into an open-access ice-flow model.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet-climate models.

We have improved the representation of subglacial water fluxes due to frictional heat production at the base of the Antarctic Ice Sheet and integrated this in an ice-sheet model. This allows for a better

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the 'deep uncertainty' in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

Uncertainties in basal melting of ice shelves, and their stability, make up the deep uncertainty of the AIS freshwater flux. A new framework for calculating subglacial water fluxes from the interior of the Antarctic Ice Sheet into the Southern Ocean presented here incorporates improved physics and reduces this uncertainty by providing a novel quantitative estimate of basal meltwater fluxes

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

Our results can be used as freshwater inputs in ocean-circulation models. This will affect the stratification of the ocean and its response to global warming. Our results will be used by modellers investigating this response.

O6: Assess the ocean impact on key global climate metrics from polar ice-sheet melt to 2300 and beyond.

The result from this study enables oceanographers to investigate the impact of previously ill-constrained meltwater sources to the ocean by incorporating the dataset that we produced.

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

All our results are open access. We have provided our new modelling framework as an open-access repository on GitHub and included this in an open-access ice-sheet model used by various groups worldwide.